

CM4AI Data Dictionary Requirements

A Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence Standards Module Deliverable

Version 1.0 – 2022/09/28

Authors:

Timothy Clark^{1*}, Sadnan Al Manir¹, Jing Chen², Christopher Churas², Erin Jeffery¹, Maxwell Adam Levinson¹, Dexter Pratt², Sarah Ratcliffe¹, Nathan Sheffield¹, Gloria Sheynkman¹, Aidong Zhang¹

¹ University of Virginia, Charlottesville VA; ² University of California San Diego, San Diego CA

* contact: Tim Clark, twc8q@virginia.edu

Abstract

This document presents requirements for a project-wide Data Dictionary (DD) to support FAIRness of data and software across the Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) project. This product will be the central tool for alignment, validation, standardization, machine-readable specification, interoperability, and required human comprehension, of all CM4AI data elements.

1 Introduction

The goal of the Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) project is to develop integrated maps of cell architecture, components, and component function based on high-throughput experimental data and a visual machine learning (ML) architecture. Output data from this effort will be engineered for uptake and reuse by advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) platforms, including machine learning / deep learning (ML/DL) architectures. The datasets and rich metadata produced will provide comprehensive FAIRness (Findability - Accessibility - Interoperability - Reusability) of both data [1] and software [2, 3] in AI-ready reuse patterns.

Rich metadata including provenance and replication packages provided on the data, software, and complex computations in this project, will support extensive data and software replication and reuse. They will enhance the project's ability to control for data stability, and to enable reliable domain-based feature engineering through detailed provenance graphs. They will provide foundational prerequisites for AI pre-model explainability [4, 5], based on extended metadata models and machine-interpretable computation histories [6, 7]. The CM4AI Standards Module in collaboration with CM4AI Tools and Data Acquisition Modules will develop a FAIR data, software, and provenance platform based on the FAIRSCAPE framework and the EVI Ontology, to support the above effort (Figure 1). This framework and its ontology have already been applied to compute and organize thousands of predictive biomedical computations on vital signs time series from neonatal ICU infants [8].

A comprehensive data dictionary (CM4AI DD) will be central to constructing this platform and to the overall goals of this project. It has a particularly important role to play in harmonization of data elements between the three distinct Data Acquisition pipelines, the Tools integration pipeline, and the Standards Module's FAIRSCAPE delivery platform. It will be an essential tool in providing interpretability, reusability, and reliability of CM4AI results, and of operationalizing their reuse for AI researchers. It will serve CM4AI development staff in Tools, Data Acquisition, and Standards; the Teaming, Ethics, and Workforce modules; the Bridge Center and NIH staff; and future users of the CM4AI data outputs in the biomedical AI community.

Requirements for this data dictionary were determined by careful review of the FAIR data and software literature; the CM4AI Module Statements of Work for each module; additional information on processing and data formats from the Data Acquisition module; and by in-depth

discussions conducted by team members of CM4AI Tools and Standards Modules during September 2022. Additional comments were also sought from all Module leads of Data Acquisition and Teaming Modules, with final approval required by the CM4AI Contact Principal Investigator.

2 Purpose: FAIR Interoperability and Human/Machine Interpretability

The CM4AI Standards Module, in close collaboration with the Tools module, is responsible for producing a comprehensive data dictionary as part of the CM4AI effort, to support FAIR interoperability and human/machine accessibility and interpretability of CM4AI digital objects [9]. The data dictionary will provide definitions, validation criteria, and examples, for metadata and data elements across the project. It will encompass raw data inputs, outputs, and processing steps from four discrete computational pipelines with the following functions.

Figure 1: FAIRSCAPE integration with CM4AI Tools and Data pipelines. FAIRSCAPE holds comprehensive FAIR metadata and deep provenance graphs on all CM4AI data objects. Data is held locally or otherwise in the most convenient location, accessed through Data URIs in the CM4AI metadata.

2.1 Spatial Proteomics - Immunofluorescence Microscopy (I-M) Data¹

This data acquisition task will map and analyze organization of key chromatin modifiers involved in cancer at a subcellular level. It will leverage the Human Protein Atlas antibody resource to undertake approximately 5,000 immunostaining experiments providing images of 1 million cells. With novel insights into spatial regulation and cross-talk of metabolic and epigenetic pathways contributing to the maintenance of cell identity and its rewiring upon state transitions and in diseased states, alongside a comprehensive catalog of image data to inform AI/ML research. The Data Dictionary will catalog raw image data, manual annotations, pipeline software, and results from this process.

¹ From Data Acquisition Module Statement of Work

2.2 Protein-Protein Interaction - Affinity purification mass spectroscopy (AP-MS) data²

Affinity purification with mass spectrometry (AP-MS) approaches will be applied to map the interactome of chromatin modifiers involved in cancer and other cell lines, providing new dynamic understanding of chromatin remodeling complexes following chemotherapy treatment of cancer cells and other interventions on iPSCs, for over 5,000 specific interactions. The Data Dictionary will enable a catalog of raw data, pipeline software, results, and provenance from this process to be produced, with standardized names, definitions, validation rules, formats, schemas, and mappings.

2.3 Genetic Interaction - Combinatorial single-cell CRISPR screens (CRISPR / scRNAseq) data¹

This Data Acquisition pipeline will organize and process single-cell CRISPR screens perturbing 100 chromatin regulators in cancer and iPSC cell lines in the presence/absence of two cell cycle drugs to assay transcriptome-wide impact of gene perturbations. The goal of these experiments is to unravel mechanisms contributing to the maintenance of cell identity and its rewiring upon state transitions and in diseased states and informing AI/ML research on systematic genotype-phenotype mapping. The Data Dictionary will model raw data, pipeline software, and results from this process.

2.4 Integrated Data, Cell Maps, and Genotype-Phenotype Models

The Tools Pipeline will combine data outputs from 2.1-2.3 to produce an integrated dataset, cell maps, and genotype-phenotype models.

2.4.1 Integrated Data

These data are embeddings that integrate the information in the base data.

2.4.2 Cell Maps

Cell Maps data are models derived from the integrated data that map the spatiotemporal architecture of human cells.

2.4.3 Genotype-Phenotype Models.

Genotype-phenotype data are produced by machine learning models that predict phenotype from genotype derived from the cell maps data; are interpretable via an internal structure based on the cell map; whose architecture is ultimately defined by the experimental data and the model analytics.

2.5 Software

All CM4AI software is included in the notion of “data” as presented in this data dictionary. Software source code and/or containers will be mapped and integrated as part of object provenance. The specific software version used to generate any dataset(s) or data objects will be registered and stored with appropriate software-specific metadata in FAIRSCAPE.

3 Personas and Use Cases: Human Accessibility and Affordances

The CM4AI Data Dictionary will provide affordances for human accessibility to FAIRSCAPE, Tools, and Data Acquisition development staff, the CM4AI Steering Committee, NIH Program Officers and other officials, and ML/DL developers and researchers; as well as for machine accessibility to CM4AI software agents in the Data and Tools pipelines, and in the FAIRSCAPE digital commons. The Data Dictionary will serve as a classic Starr-Griesemer “boundary object” [10–12] mediating many technical interactions between CM4AI researchers, developers, and

² From Data Acquisition Module Statement of Work

users. Thus it is not to be treated as a static piece of documentation or a checklist item. The personas below have specific interactions with the CM4AI DD.

3.1 CM4AI Bioinformatics development staff

The Data Dictionary will provide standardized definitions of (meta)data element names, data types, meaning, interpretation, and validation rules for clarity and consistency in building and modifying the three CM4AI processing and one integration pipelines.

3.2 CM4AI Pipeline computational agents

The Data Dictionary will provide machine-interpretable validation rules as input to automated validators to ensure inputs to computational agents in the CM4AI pipelines are correct, meaningful, and processable.

3.3 CM4AI FAIRSCAPE developers

CM4AI will use the FAIRSCAPE computational data commons and the EVI Evidence Graph Ontology as key components to register and vend results data, ensuring comprehensive FAIRness at all stages (see Figure 1). The Data Dictionary and validators will provide assurance that data entering the FAIRSCAPE framework is computationally valid and in "pre-FAIR" status, i.e. that it can be made FAIR. Data not having standardized cross-project names, for example, or with undefined meanings, cannot be properly made FAIR as it will not become interoperable. Conformance of terms with the EVI ontology will play a key role in this regard.

3.4 NIH Program Officers and Other Institute Staff

The CM4AI Data Dictionary will be a tool to enable insight by Program Officers and others at NIH into the meaning of CM4AI results, support program reviews via a Results Portal, and in conjunction with the validation toolkit, provide quality assurance on program results.

3.5 ML/DL Investigators

We intend that ML/DL investigators will be enabled to reuse and re-purpose the CM4AI outputs in various exciting and innovative ways as AI technology and applications in computational biology, healthcare, and therapy development continue to progress. The data dictionary, by enabling interoperability and re-usability of the data, will be an essential resource enabling these types of reuse. In conjunction with the rest of the FAIRSCAPE platform and the EVI ontology, it will help provide a basis for future work to provide ML/DL premodel explainability and beyond that, detailed biomedical interpretability of results.

Pre-model explainability - the ability to comprehend input features, what they mean, where they came from in domain context, and how their modifications and statistical characteristics affect the modeling process - requires a grounded understanding of data definitions, characteristics, meaning, and detailed provenance as a prerequisite. In addition, the various sources of potential data variation must be understood and controllable. In sophisticated instrumentation systems, including robotic processes and complex analytic pipelines, only rich metadata and deep provenance graphs can provide such information. CM4AI will build these capabilities into its process through its metadata model, data dictionary, and provenance ontology.

4 Data Dictionary Structure and Components

4.1 Machine Accessibility and Interpretability

The CM4AI Data Dictionary will be machine accessible and interpretable [11] to integrate at a software level with validation and FAIRSCAPE metadata transfer agents within the Data and Tools pipelines. It will be provided in a recognized format such as YAML, JSON, JSON-LD,

and/or .csv and will map standard, localized CM4AI data element names to clearly equivalent standard ontology terms where applicable.

Where EVI Evidence Graph Ontology terms are mappable, they will be used as the Global Mapping terms. This supports proper integration into FAIRSCAPE.

The Portable Encapsulated Project (PEP) [13] model is an interesting instance of how for example, YAML and .csv can be combined to define datasets, and aspects of this approach may be adopted to provide sample-level validation capabilities with integration to various workflow systems. We envision interoperability with PEP as a goal for the CM4AI DD design.

4.2 Components

The CM4AI Data Dictionary will contain metadata models at five interacting metadata levels:

- Object,
- Format,
- Schema,
- Release, and
- License,

as shown in Figure 2, with reference by URI (in the Object metadata) to the Object Content.

There should be one Object metadata specification, common across all digital Objects; a small set of Format specifications (e.g. Immunofluorescence Image, CSV, etc.) which describe the digital formats used in the various Objects, and referred to in the Object specification; and one or more Schema specifications for each Format specification, describing any variations of data arrangement within a given Format. There will be a Release specification for a given set of Objects and Contents, describing the data Release availability and status; and one distinct License specification describing the CM4AI data license, availability, and terms of use for the Object data.

Figure 2. Entity-relationship diagram for CM4AI Object, Format, Schema, Release, and License metadata requirements, with their relationship to the actual object contents.

Metadata for each Object shall be a union of elements specified by these six levels, based on the standard Object metadata, the specific Format and Schema of the data being described, the Release it belongs to, and its license and availability. When the metadata for an object is viewed, the complete metadata values will be presented.

Object content (i.e. the specific data instantiated in the object) must be held separately from the metadata, as required in [1, 9] and accessible by reference to its content URI. So for example a BioPlex protein embedding would have metadata consisting of the union of elements in (1) the Object metadata, (2) the CSV Format, and (3) the BioPlex protein embedding Schema; with details of a specific data (4) Release, and the applicable (5) License terms and availability .

- **Object** metadata is required to follow a common model across CM4AI digital objects, specified by the Data Dictionary, and must describe the Object's unique identity, name, description, authorship, provenance, and related information.
- **Object** metadata should be similar to and largely mappable to that provided by NIH "General purpose" FAIR digital repositories such as Dataverse and/or by the Datacite DOI registration agency.
 - Mandatory data elements will include a persistent identifier [14, 15]; name and description; author or creator; creation date; version; provenance information; access permissions; and data object URI.
 - The preferred mappings for Object metadata will be to Schema.org [16] or Bioschemas.org [17] terms as dominant standards in this field.
 - Object metadata is intended to support interoperability with NIH-approved general purpose and domain-specific repositories and with the EVI ontology [18,19] used in FAIRSCAPE.
- **Format** metadata is required to describe specific file formats and provide access, interpretation, visualization methods, and examples for a specific type or class of object. For example, a CSV object with visualization via Excel; or a mass spectroscopy mzML output file with reading and visualization via multiple readers and viewers. Format metadata must be provided to support interoperability with, and human/machine interpretability of, the various file types in CM4AI pipelines.
 - Mandatory metadata elements will include
 - format name, e.g. "mzML" [20],
 - format description, e.g. "mzML open source raw mass spec file format"
 - documentationURL, e.g. <https://www.psidev.info/mzML>,
 - references for the relevant publications, e.g. "Deutsch 2010 Methods Mol. Bio. 604: 319–331. doi:10.1007/978-1-60761-444-9_22",
 - preferred format readers, e.g. "R reader (mzR), python reader (pymzml)", with links to package source code.
 - Preferred term mappings are schema.org terms, e.g. <format> should map to, or be represented as, <https://schema.org/encodingFormat>.
- **Schema** metadata must describe the specific content organization schema of a given object, which may vary within format types. It should have a many-to-one relation with Format metadata elements. That is, for a given class / format, such as CSV structure, the metadata elements represented in that structure will fall into one or more Schema types, depending upon the type of content being represented in the format.
 - Mandatory metadata elements must include
 - schema name, e.g. "mzML XSD",
 - associated format, e.g. "mzML",
 - format description,
 - formal schema specification, in gitHub or other repository, which may be:
 - a list of <element: datatype: definition: validation rule> tuples for each data element in the data content referenced by the objectURI;

- or for XML schemas, an XSD file, e.g. https://github.com/HUPO-PSI/mzML/blob/master/schema/schema_1.1/mzML1.1.1_idx.xsd,
- or other formal schema model.
 - Preferred term mappings to domain-associated ontology properties.
- Metadata to provide further human accessibility beyond text definitions may be included as additional elements to support human and machine accessibility and portal display, e.g. visualized data examples, search keywords, etc.
- **Release** metadata describes a specific dataset release package, its version, status, license, availability, and terms of use.
- **License** metadata describes a specific content license, such as (for data) a Creative Commons license; terms of use and availability.
- **Content** of the actual object is held separately, optionally remotely, and referenced by resolving the contentURI in the Object metadata.

4.3 Component Relationships

4.3.1 Relationship to the Evidence Graph Ontology

EVI, the Evidence Graph Ontology [8, 18], an OWL2 [19] ontology, is used to organize and provide FAIRness within the FAIRSCAPE framework and the CM4AI project. All EVI datatype properties will be included in the data dictionary.

4.3.2 Relationship to the Validators

Validation tools / agents will base their determination of validity of each data element in an incoming or outgoing dataset, in any of the Tools or Data Acquisition pipelines, on executable validation rule(s) corresponding to the data element in the dictionary.

4.3.3 Relationship to the Portal

The FAIRSCAPE related CM4AI FAIR Data Access portal will need to provide accessibility to CM4AI data and the data dictionary. It could potentially be accessed from the Bridge Portal or a CM4AI-specific data access portal linked to the Bridge Center website (preferable).

4.3.4 Relationship to the Cell Maps / Cell Architecture Ontology and Other Standardization Work

A goal of CM4AI Standards beyond Year 1 is to develop a formal ontology of Cell Maps and Cell Architecture. This will of necessity focus on the final outputs of CM4AI and their knowledge content and structure. Components of the Data Dictionary after further validation in the CM4AI process can make an important contribution to the development of such an ontology. They can also after suitable generalization contribute to standardization of other project data dictionaries.

5 Development Approach: MuSIC Data and CM4AI

The pipelines for the three Data Acquisition pipelines and the Tools pipeline currently are run at different locations and institutions, within diverse computational environments, and have numerous elements under development. The Data and Tools pipelines appear to vary in their degree of formalization. And the CRISPR scRNAseq data pipeline will not be added until year 2.

This requires us to develop the Data Dictionary in a series of successive versions, using preliminary AP-MS and localization data from the MuSIC project [21], for testing and validation in our collaboration and development efforts, and then developing versions with successively greater comprehensiveness.

The Data Dictionary will be refined from its initial version based on MuSIC to later encompass the full array of Data and Tools components, with increasingly finer-grained representations.

CRISPR scRNAseq elements will be added in the second year, and improvements will continue to be made throughout the life of the project.

Thus, there will be evolving versions of the data dictionary as development proceeds.

It should also be evident that granularity of operations is an important consideration. Our initial CM4AI data dictionary will encompass raw data and processed results from the Data Acquisition pipelines, and multiple stages in the Tools pipeline as appropriate, including final results of each pipeline.

Later versions will comprehend finer-grained provenance and additional pipeline elements.

6 Conclusion

The above requirements will guide iterative development of the CM4 Data Dictionary. We project a significant need to publish multiple revisions of CM4AI DD as the project develops and new requirements surface which may not be visible today. The Data Dictionary Requirements are a roadmap to develop the initial version in this series, and to guide development of future versions.

7 REFERENCES

1. Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A.J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C.T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A.J.G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J.S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P.A.C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S.J., Martone, M.E., Mons, A., Packer, A.L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M.A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., Mons, B.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*. 3, 160018 (2016).
2. Lamprecht, A.-L., Garcia, L., Kuzak, M., Martinez, C., Arcila, R., Martin Del Pico, E., Dominguez Del Angel, V., van de Sandt, S., Ison, J., Martinez, P.A., McQuilton, P., Valencia, A., Harrow, J., Psomopoulos, F., Gelpi, J.LI., Chue Hong, N., Goble, C., Capella-Gutierrez, S.: Towards FAIR principles for research software. *DS*. 3, 37–59 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>.
3. Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F.E., Harrow, J., Castro, L.J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P.A., Honeyman, T.: FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles). (2021). <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00065>.
4. Markus, A.F., Kors, J.A., Rijnbeek, P.R.: The role of explainability in creating trustworthy artificial intelligence for health care: A comprehensive survey of the terminology, design choices, and evaluation strategies. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*. 113, 103655 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2020.103655>.
5. the Precise4Q consortium, Amann, J., Blasimme, A., Vayena, E., Frey, D., Madai, V.I.: Explainability for artificial intelligence in healthcare: a multidisciplinary perspective. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak*. 20, 310 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-020-01332-6>.
6. Gil, Y., Miles, S., Belhajjame, K., Deus, H., Garijo, D., Klyne, G., Missier, P., Soiland-Reyes, S., Zednik, S.: PROV Model Primer: W3C Working Group Note 30 April 2013, <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-primer/>, (2013).
7. Al Manir, S., Niestroy, J., Levinson, M.A., Clark, T.: Evidence Graphs: Supporting Transparent and FAIR Computation, with Defeasible Reasoning on Data, Methods, and Results. In: Glavic, B., Braganholo, V., and Koop, D. (eds.) *Provenance and Annotation of*

- Data and Processes. pp. 39–50. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2021).
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80960-7_3.
8. Niestroy, J.C., Moorman, J.R., Levinson, M.A., Manir, S.A., Clark, T.W., Fairchild, K.D., Lake, D.E.: Discovery of signatures of fatal neonatal illness in vital signs using highly comparative time-series analysis. *npj Digit. Med.* 5, 6 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00551-z>.
 9. Starr, J., Castro, E., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Downs, R.R., Duerr, R., Haak, L.L., Haendel, M., Herman, I., Hodson, S., Hourclé, J., Kratz, J.E., Lin, J., Nielsen, L.H., Nurnberger, A., Proell, S., Rauber, A., Sacchi, S., Smith, A., Taylor, M., Clark, T.: Achieving human and machine accessibility of cited data in scholarly publications. *PeerJ Computer Science.* 1, e1 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1>.
 10. Star, S.L., Griesemer, J.R.: Institutional Ecology, “Translations” and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley’s Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907-39. *Social Studies of Science.* 19, 387–420 (1989).
 11. Star, S.L.: The structure of ill-structured solutions: boundary objects and heterogeneous distributed problem solving. In: *Distributed Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 2)*. pp. 37–54. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc. (1989).
 12. Star, S.L.: This is Not a Boundary Object: Reflections on the Origin of a Concept. *Science, Technology & Human Values.* 35, 601–617 (2010).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243910377624>.
 13. Sheffield, N.C., Stolarczyk, M., Reuter, V.P., Rendeiro, A.F.: Linking big biomedical datasets to modular analysis with Portable Encapsulated Projects. *Gigascience.* 10, giab077 (2021).
 14. McMurry, J.A., Juty, N., Blomberg, N., Burdett, T., Conlin, T., Conte, N., Courtot, M., Deck, J., Dumontier, M., Fellows, D.K., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gormanns, P., Grethe, J., Hastings, J., Hériché, J.-K., Hermjakob, H., Ison, J.C., Jimenez, R.C., Jupp, S., Kunze, J., Laibe, C., Le Novère, N., Malone, J., Martin, M.J., McEntyre, J.R., Morris, C., Muilu, J., Müller, W., Rocca-Serra, P., Sansone, S.-A., Sariyar, M., Snoep, J.L., Soiland-Reyes, S., Stanford, N.J., Swainston, N., Washington, N., Williams, A.R., Wimalaratne, S.M., Winfree, L.M., Wolstencroft, K., Goble, C., Mungall, C.J., Haendel, M.A., Parkinson, H.: Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. *PLoS Biol.* 15, e2001414 (2017).
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>.
 15. Juty, N., Wimalaratne, S.M., Soiland-Reyes, S., Kunze, J., Goble, C.A., Clark, T.: Unique, Persistent, Resolvable: Identifiers as the Foundation of FAIR. *Data Intelligence.* 2, 30–39 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00025.
 16. Guha, R.V., Brickley, D., Macbeth, S.: Schema.org: evolution of structured data on the web. *Communications of the ACM.* 59, 44–51 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2844544>.
 17. Bioschemas.org: Bioschemas, <https://bioschemas.org>, (2022).
 18. Al Manir, S., Niestroy, J., Levinson, M., Clark, T.: EVI: The Evidence Graph Ontology, OWL 2 Vocabulary, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4630931>, (2021).
 19. OWL 2 Working Group: OWL 2 Web Ontology Language: W3C Recommendation 27 October 2009. World Wide Web Consortium, Cambridge MA, US (2009).
 20. Deutsch, E.W.: Mass Spectrometer Output File Format mzML. In: Hubbard, S.J. and Jones, A.R. (eds.) *Proteome Bioinformatics*. pp. 319–331. Humana Press, Totowa, NJ (2010). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-60761-444-9_22
 21. Qin, Y., Huttlin, E.L., Winsnes, C.F., Gosztyla, M.L., Wacheul, L., Kelly, M.R., Blue, S.M., Zheng, F., Chen, M., Schaffer, L.V., Licon, K., Bäckström, A., Vaites, L.P., Lee, J.J., Ouyang, W., Liu, S.N., Zhang, T., Silva, E., Park, J., Pitea, A., Kreisberg, J.F., Gygi, S.P., Ma, J., Harper, J.W., Yeo, G.W., Lafontaine, D.L.J., Lundberg, E., Ideker, T.: A multi-

scale map of cell structure fusing protein images and interactions. *Nature*. 600, 536–542 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-04115-9>.